

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INNOVATIVE METHODS AND APPROACHES IN TEACHING NATIVE LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article presents theories about the importance of using various approaches and methods in methodology of teaching the native language, in particular, opinions about the benefits of using various approaches and methods in teaching vocabulary are central. The article can be used by students, teachers of higher educational institutions and teachers of secondary schools.*

Keywords: *native language teaching methodology, educational process, modern education, lexical approach, traditional and innovative teaching methods, vocabulary, interactive methods.*

We know from different eras of education, the importance of applying different approaches to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, and the effective use of various methods in the meaningful organization of lesson processes has always been considered important and significant. It is no secret that high results can be achieved in a short time using such approaches and methods. Therefore, in modern education, great attention is paid to various approaches and methods. These approaches and methods, by their nature, increase the cognitive activity of students, allow them to work in small groups and teams, freely express their personal views on the studied topic, problems, justify their opinions with evidence, among the opinions it acquires special importance as it can form the skills of choosing the most necessary solution.

The current stage of the development of the methodology of teaching the mother tongue is distinguished by various working styles and methods, among which one can find traditional and innovative methods and approaches. This diversity is related to the historical features of language teaching in different periods and the goals of the teacher in the work process. Traditionally, language teaching has focused on the development of grammatical skills, since grammar is the foundation of any language. However, the increasing popularity of the communicative method of teaching the native language teaching method forces teachers to look for ways to enable learners to use the knowledge they have acquired in real life as easily and quickly as possible. For example, one of these methods is the lexical approach proposed by English linguist Michael Lewis at the end of the 20th century.

Today, the use of the lexical approach in the process of teaching students the methodology of teaching the native language allows to achieve great progress in this subject. In particular, to turn the lexical approach into an effective tool for teaching and learning native language teaching methods, to form the ability of students to use the studied topics and problems in real educational conditions, to achieve fluency in speech, and to stimulate activity. It is possible to achieve an effective result. We should not forget to pay attention to the place of the lexical approach in the system of methodological tools and methods, to analyze its positive features, necessary conditions for its use, and the possible results of educational activities.

It should also be said that the use of interactive methods in the lesson processes related to the teaching of the mother tongue teaching methodology is also effective. In particular,

elucidation of topics and problems related to word groups with the help of new technologies not only serves to further improve students' knowledge of the Department of Morphology, but also enriches the knowledge related to this department with new views, conclusions, and theories.

The new content of education is to ensure that today's students are not only literate and knowledgeable, but also able to explain the theory in practical work and master the educational material at the level required by the student's needs in order to carefully organize the lessons of the mother tongue in the future. refers to the cultivation of For this purpose, effective use of interactive and modern educational methods at the stages of teaching the mother tongue teaching methodology will give good results in order to encourage them to be active and apply the theory in practical processes at the right point. Simply teaching the noun phrase in native language classes through the use of problem-based learning opportunities teaches students to successfully perform logical-linguistic work methods, equips them with intellectual and practical methods of activity, the legal rules of the phrase and the word. Students will learn the skills of independent work with phrases, sentences and texts, creative mastery of language features and its laws, and the formation of skills for creative use of it in written and oral speech. Creates the imagination of such skills to work with students in the future.

It can be concluded from the above that searching for new ways to achieve efficiency in education and its proper application in practical processes always gives good results in any period. It is desirable to expand students' knowledge using innovative methods, new approaches, unique methods. Teaching to students the methodology of teaching the mother tongue and teaching them using innovative methods and approaches in the teaching process will be the foundation for educating them in the future as educated, free-expressing, independent-minded students.

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